

Guided Customization for Learning Objects

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Abstract. In recent years, the idea of open software has expanded and involved several new types of applications with the intention of democratizing information and knowledge. In the educational context, this idea has been evolved and called open educational resources (OER). One of the characteristics of OER is that users (i.e., teachers and students) can adapt the educational software to their needs. This adaptation is only feasible if users have access to software codes and expertise to perform the adaptation. However, adjustments for the OER community are quite specific and require the direct intervention of a teacher who usually does not have skills to perform technical changes. This work then describes a strategy for adapting Learning Objects (LO), called guided customization. This strategy proposes that, at the design step, the LO development team states precisely what resources can be adapted. Similarly, users of these resources will be associated with profiles indicating which level of adaptation, depending on their qualification, can be accomplished without, however, compromising the pedagogical content of the resource. Thus, resources can be customized by users at execution time, making the real benefits of OER become evident in practice.

Resumo. Nos últimos anos, a ideia de software livre tem se expandido e envolvido vários novos tipos de aplicativos com o intuito de democratizar a informação e o conhecimento. No meio educacional, esta ideia evoluiu e foi chamada de recurso educacional aberto (REA). Por exemplo, uma das características do REA é que os usuários (ou seja, professores e alunos) possam adaptar o software às suas necessidades educacionais. Esta adaptação só é viável se os usuários tiverem acesso aos códigos do software e expertise para realizar a adaptação. No entanto, os ajustes para a comunidade REA são bastante específicos e requerem a intervenção direta de um professor que geralmente não tem as habilidades para realizar alterações técnicas. Este trabalho então descreve uma estratégia para adaptar Objetos de Aprendizagem (LO), denominada customização guiada. Esta estratégia propõe que, na etapa de design, sejam indicados os recursos que podem ser

adaptados. Da mesma forma, os usuários desses recursos serão associados com perfis indicando qual o nível de adaptação, dependendo de sua qualificação, pode ser realizado sem, no entanto, comprometer o conteúdo pedagógico do recurso. Assim, os recursos podem ser personalizados pelos usuários em tempo de execução, tornando os reais benefícios do REA evidenciados na prática.

Introduction

In terms of globalization, sharing is not only an option but a demand, especially when information and knowledge are involved [SOUZA et al, 2011]. This idea first came up when some movements were created in order to support democratic knowledge sharing.

One of these movements that was highly responsible for this democratization is called *Open Source*. According to the Open Source Initiative (OSI), *open source* is a movement focused on software development and its distribution. Developing software according to open source philosophy requires that its source code must be opened. In addition to this, free distribution, derived works, license distribution and neutral distribution concerning technology must be guaranteed [OPEN SOURCE].

Open Source was established from the movement called free software in the 90's, as an alternative to the software industry whose point of view concerning the same software differs from the open source philosophy [OPEN SOURCE].

Another aspect that must be taken into consideration that is seen by both movements as essential to spreading knowledge is the collaborative idea. In this opening and collaborative environment that supports knowledge and information sharing, a movement in favor of opening educational resources has arisen, called OPEN EDUCATIONAL RESOURCE (OER), directed to sharing resources for the educational environment.

The acronym OER first appeared in 2002 at the UNESCO conference and it can be defined as digital educational materials freely available to those who use

them for teaching, learning and research [HILEN, 2006].

According to Hilen (2006), OER is a new phenomenon that is part of a bigger opening in colleges and universities, and includes other well-known, world-wide and established movements, such as Open Source Software (OSS) and Open Access (OA).

Instead of lack of educational resources, in this new age of technology, we have an availability of content, resources, teaching and also open architecture concerning virtual and physical spaces that have open code and knowledge [BATSON et al, 2008].

To Hilen (2006), this kind of opening must occur at an availability level as well as in usage, without technical, financial or legal problems for the target user. Thus, users will be able not only to use or read the resource, but they also will be able to adapt and therefore reuse it.

The possibility of modifying a resource, or even sharing it inside or outside its country are important issues for educational policies, since new demands in educational systems have arisen due to recent developments in communication and information technologies [DAGIENE and ZILINSKIENE, 2009].

In this chapter, we intend to explore feasible ways for building and reusing Digital Educational Resources (DER) in the form of Learning Objects (LO), based on an adaptation strategy used in its development process.

Adaptation of Digital Educational Resources

Since OER are shared worldwide, there is a need to adapt them to different users. In this section, the concept of adaptation is discussed in the perspective of Software Engineering.

The word adaptation in software was used to mean techniques used to rearrange parts of previously developed software and then reuse them in new systems [CANAL et al, 2006]. Adaptation can be done in two ways, dynamically

and statically [ROCHA et al, 2007]. The first is at a system level which is called personalization. The second is at an interface level called customization [FREUND, 2009].

Personalization must not be confused with customization. While customization is related to changing, shaping or modifying a product or service according to the user's needs, personalization involves intense communication and interaction between users and suppliers [FREUND, 2009].

In order to answer the globalization call to overcome all barriers, adaptation has been claimed as a resource to bring a higher number of people much closer. Thus, localization and internationalization techniques are highly valued, as follows [PRUDÊNCIO et al, 2005].

According to Prudêncio et al (2005), internationalization (also known as I18N) is a step in a software's development process that is responsible for adapting it and making it neutral in terms of legal, financial and cultural relationships in a country. International software must accept, for instance, different orders of numbers and algorithms that follow different rules in many different languages. In order to implement these characteristics some suitable procedures should be used to adequately localize the software.

Localization (also known as L10N) is the second step to be taken to prepare software for the international market. This is when the adaptation for a specific locale will be designed. It involves translation, cultural adaptation, standardization and characteristics of the target market.

Figure 1. Relationship Between Software Internationalization and Localization

Figure 1 shows the dependency between these two techniques. According to the Localization Industry Standard Association (LISA), making software localizable implies making it linguistically and culturally adapted to the target region (country, region and language) where the software will be used [PRUDÊNCIO et al, 2005].

Although localization is a way of reducing the distance between software and users, for Amiel et al (2009), this strategy is not suitable when the focus is only on language translation. The design context is very important and must be taken into consideration.

Among all discussions concerning the possible paths of DER, a strategy for the creation of an adaptable LO is proposed in [SOUZA et al, 2010] and [SOUZA et al, 2011], called guided customization, and will be presented in the following section.

Guided Customization

The localization technique used in the software is capable of adapting it to any user. This technique is a kind of personalization and, as previously stated, it can adapt the system to its user. This technique actually allows the content to be adapted to different needs. However, to achieve this goal it is necessary to modify

the software source code.

Software localization is not an easy task because it requires specific knowledge to make the changes [SOUZA et al, 2010]. However, if the software is of an educational type, in which teachers and students are clients and users, respectively, this technique is not efficient, because it does not allow the adaptations to be done by the interested parties.

In this context, an adaptation strategy called guided customization is proposed in [SOUZA et al, 2010] and [SOUZA et al, 2011], and presented as follows. This strategy is based on customization of learning objects (LO), which allows clients to change or reconfigure the software's interface in order to adapt it to its new scenarios.

Guided customization allows one to execute adaptation in elements found in the LO, such as activities and their levels, buttons, text, video, image and audio. Another advantage in this strategy is that multicultural aspects can be more easily addressed, because teachers can take into consideration cultural diversity in their experience, thus, helping students to have more appropriate learning resources.

Figure 2. Guided Customization in the DER Development and Use

The guided customization strategy was developed to be used both during the conceptualization stage and during the use of the resource. Figure 2 shows the stages for the production of digital educational resources (DER), showing how guided customization is present in both stages, which are detailed in the next sections.

Guided Customization in the Conceptualization Stage

Creating a DER must begin in the conceptualization stage. During this stage, a description of each resource's scenarios is conducted, while decisions about what can and cannot be changed are made.

Each described scenario is formed by elements and actions with pedagogical potential, understood as the possibility of representing a concept. In this chapter, pedagogical potential is defined as the capacity that an element or action has, alone or in combination with other elements, to express or represent a specific concept, thus allowing its understanding. The elements of pedagogical potential that can be part of a DER include: text, images, buttons, videos and audios. A combination of elements can be used as a strategy to improve the learning process. That's why the conceptualization stage is the most important stage in the development process.

In this stage the developed resource's scope and its area are defined and a document called *storyboard* is produced to guide the implementation stage. The *storyboard* is a document used to represent the elements and actions that will be part of the resource. They are exactly the elements or actions that may be chosen to be customized and have to be carefully selected in order to maintain the DER learning goals, even if they are changed.

Once the elements and actions more likely to be altered have been identified, the resource goes into the development stage. During this stage, the professionals in charge will be responsible for implementing what was defined in the storyboard, including the customization of elements and actions previously

determined.

Figure 3 shows the interface design proposed and Figure 4 shows the screen of a LO developed from these elements. Two kinds of elements that can be customized are found on the screen (text and buttons).

Figure 3. Interface Design of Activity 1 of the DER Customized Amazing Stories

Figure 4. Interface of Activity 1 of the Customized DER Amazing Stories

The kind of customization that can be done on the element has to be specified. In the example in Figure 4, the user is allowed to edit the element text

and to turn on and off the element button.

The advantage of this approach is that adaptation is done by the client at the LO interface level, breaking the rule that only people with programming skill is able to modify or adapt a DER.

The approach used on guided customization aims to change the thought that planning must fit the resource, and it also makes it possible to fit the resource to the planning, giving more autonomy to teachers.

In the following section, the implications of guided customization on using a customized LO will be discussed.

Use of Guided Customization

In this chapter, DER can be classified in two categories: Adaptable (A) and Non-Adaptable (NA) (Figure 5). The latter concerns developed DER, but it does not have elements with pedagogical potential. That does not mean that the resource has inferior technical and pedagogical quality compared to those with this potential. On the other hand, Adaptable DER have elements with pedagogical potential elements and must offer advantages in order to be adapted.

As shown in Figure 5, concerning the kind of adaptation (A) possible, resources are divided into two forms: personalized (P), where localization (L) is contemplated, and customizable (C). In this chapter, three levels of customization are proposed: Basic (b), Intermediate (i) and Advanced (a). The number of elements with pedagogical potential available in the DER will define the level of customization.

Figure 5. DER Classification According to its Capacity of Adaptation

The basic level of customization offers only customization of button elements. The intermediate level offers button and text elements, and the advanced level offers customization of audio and video, plus text and button elements.

Thus, guided customization strategy aims to facilitate the development of customizable LO and aims to make it possible for teachers to make their own adaptation of DER, regardless of the original language, country or culture in which it was developed. In order to help teachers and also attend to their level of knowledge, this chapter presents the definition of degree of freedom, which is the permission given to a client to modify a LO, taking into consideration his/her level of interest and knowledge.

The degree of freedom (DF) aims to permit adjustments to be carried out on the resource considering the number of elements with pedagogical potential and the level of knowledge required from the client in order to perform the right adjustments.

The freedom given to a client is based on the idea of freedom disseminated by the free software movement that states: point out, without restrictions, to the kind of modification to be done on a software by somebody, rating it from 1 to 4.

Each degree allows the client to modify from the highest level (Degree 1-3, modifications on the resource interface) to the lowest level (Degree 4, modifications on the resource code).

Degree 1 or simply DF 1, allows the client activating (ON) or deactivating (OFF) a certain activities. At this level, only this kind of action will be possible.

Degree 2 or simply DF 2 is more flexible because it has the permission of DF 1 plus the actions of ability to specify frames of a video that is going to be used. Taking the specification of frames as an example, it is possible to define the upper and lower limits of the video segments to be shown to the user.

Degree 3 or simply DF 3 includes the actions of DF 1 and DF 2 besides the permission to edit or rewrite a text and replace images, audio and video. Feedback texts should not be included in this list because, if they are modified, segments from the resource code will be altered.

At this level, the client is free to make several modifications and therefore determine which conceptual sequence must be presented to the user. DF 1, DF2 and DF 3 are usually designed to those who do not wish, or do not have knowledge, to make modifications at a low level.

Finally, degree 4 or DF 4 can be considered highest level of freedom to be offered on a LO, combining the permissions of DF 1, DF 2 and DF 3 with modifications on actions at a code level.

Taking as an example a LO with an advanced level of customization, in other words, with several pedagogically potential elements (texts, feedbacks, button, audio, video), unless the permission was given to the client within the project, it is not possible to make adjustments. Examples of modifications to be done at this level, besides the ones described in DF 1, DF 2 and DF 3, are the inclusion of text feedback. Even though they are text changes, they have to be done at the code level. This kind of DF 4 permission is usually taken by those who have knowledge to make changes at a low level.

The DF tries to create a relationship between the “want to modify” and “can

modify” regarding LO use and adjustments. Thus, besides making it feasible to open the content, this freedom also aims to allow opening the resource, allowing one not only to share knowledge, but also to include new ideas. For example, Figures 6 and 7 show the customizable LO Amazing Stories and its adaptation according to DF1. The Amazing Stories LO can be defined as intermediate because it has text and button elements.

In this resource, the user has the freedom to edit a text as well as activate and deactivate activities using the buttons. The client can choose the kind of adaptation to be done. If the client chooses to only deactivate an activity, (s)he will require DF 1. This action must be carried out using *login* and password that the DER must have in order to control these permissions. After that, the resource will be available to the client, as shown in Figure 5, where the character’s speech is available to be changed.

Figure 6. Customizable DER with DF 1

If the client simultaneously chooses deactivate an activity and edit the text, (s)he must require the DF 3. This action must be carried out using *login* and password. After that, the resource will be available to the client, as shown in Figure 7, but

now the speech of the editable character is included as well as the activities with the deactivate function.

Figure 7. Customizable DER with DF 3

This freedom makes it possible to increase the teacher's autonomy, allowing for different learning opportunities. Souza et al (2007) argues in favor of the need for tools that would make this autonomy available, helping to produce a fascinating and encouraging environment for teachers and students.

Thus, we are going to discuss new perspectives in creating authoring and customization mechanisms designed to produce customizable LO.

Development Process and Authoring Tool

Before thinking about the usage of customizable LO, it is important to think about the development process used that gives support to its production, as well as the tools used.

In order to produce a LO, a multi-disciplinary team is usually required, which contains educators or instructional designers, content experts or teachers,

graphical designers and programmers.

When the developed LO has a customizable profile, the team involved in the development process is also a multidisciplinary one. However, it is not an easy task to develop resources with such characteristics, because more integration amongst all the professionals involved concerning formalism (use of diagrams) is required.

This formalism should prioritize the quality of communication among the professionals concerning the elements which should be available for changes in the LO.

Figure 8 shows the activities developed by teams and for each professionals working in the development of OA. In this process, there is not a standard for the documentation generated by each team (scope and sequence activity, modeling, animation and implementation) that promote a clear understanding of the DER requisites by all involved professionals.

In order to facilitate the development of customizable LO, a new developmental model is proposed in this chapter (Figure 9), based on model driven software engineering (MDSE - *Model Driven Software Engineering*) that uses specific languages (DSL – *Domain Specific Language*) [SCHMIDT, 2006]. These languages have representations aimed at a specific audience [SOUZA et al, 2008]. From these specifications, MDSE advises that some transformations should be applied to these models. That may be guided to any specific architecture on which codes can be created.

Figure 8. Generic Model of a Development Process of LO

Figure 9 shows a new development process based on model driven software engineering (MDSE - *Model Driven Software Engineering*) that uses specific languages (DSL – *Domain Specific Language*) [SCHMIDT, 2006]. These languages have representations aimed at a specific audience [SOUZA et al, 2008]. From these specifications, MDSE advises that some transformations should be applied to these models. That may be guided to any specific architecture on which codes can be created.

Figure 9. Development Process of MDSE based CLO

This new process allows a reproduction, while still in the project phase, of the interfaces that will be part of the object, and the relationships of dependency among them, as part of the customized learning object architecture (CLO's architecture). In order to reach this objective, a DSL is used that allows the creation of models, later used in the stages of development and implementation of the CLO.

The architectural model produced by this DSL is changed to create a plot or a storyboard that will be the basis for the production of interfaces and codes by the designers and programmers respectively.

The main idea of the MDSE is to strengthen the conceptualization stage, in order to reduce the effort in the implementation stage. In other words, the

concern is what to develop, and not how to develop [SOUZA et al, 2010].

To make the production of used documentation (templates and diagrams) easier, an authoring tool called CLO Studio was developed to build the LO's specifications and to create architectural models (Figure 10). It was developed as an Eclipse *plug-in* using the Graphic Modeling Framework (GMF) [ECLIPSE].

CLO Studio allows one to describe the LO's dynamics, the modeling of the interfaces and also the customization actions available to the user whenever the LO code is generated. Besides that, it has a metamodel and a DSL (Domain Specific Language) that will serve as a tool to build the LO.

Figure 10. Screen of the CLO Studio

Figure 11 shows the importance of CLO Studio within the development process. This tool helps pedagogues and experts during the conceptualization stage by describing the resource's architecture. This description is produced in a specific language (DSL) that offers subsidies to generate the model that will represent the resource's architecture. The generated models are also described in a XML file. These documents will be used by designers and programmers as the basis to respectively model and implement the customizable resource.

Figure 11. The Influence of CLO Studio in the DER Development

Conclusion

This chapter summarizes concepts and challenges related to OER and presents guided customization as a new approach to be used in the development and use of digital educational resources, making them customizable. This kind of approach allows increasing the resource openness, and therefore teachers' autonomy in planning is valued because there is a concern in balancing between the development and the usage of the resource.

Guided customization does not focus only on production, but also on the use of the resource, and in order to do so, it proposes the definition of pedagogical potential and degree of freedom. While the former refers to who is going to develop it, the latter refers to who it is going to use it.

Due to the concern in decreasing the distance between users of the resources and its development, guided customization allows content and resources to be equally shared.

For Wiley (2009), more than developing open content, it is necessary to effectively use them and decide how and when. One of the ways to reach this goal is by applying the 4R's (reuse, revise, remix and redistribution).

In this chapter, a process of development and an authoring tool called CLO Studio, were presented regarding the development of a LO that can be reusable. The customizable LO created is available on a *web server*.

Revise is made possible by the resource's customization characteristic. Remix is possible with the components created in the CLO Studio. Redistribution can be reached in future works with the resource's storage in a web repository.

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